

Particle Conveyance in a Particle-driven CSP Loop: Design, Operation, Attrition and Erosion

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Abstract. A novel concentrated solar power (CSP) system employing particle-driven technology is currently being scaled to multi-megawatt capacity under the EU Horizon Europe's "powder-to-powder" (P2P) initiative. The system integrates a fluidized bed-in-tube solar receiver, down-comer assembly, particle-based PV super-heater, thermal storage/power generation unit, and pneumatic particle recirculation system. Engineering analysis confirms the feasibility of conveying 16 tph particles through a 0.20 m diameter insulated vertical pipe, achieving 250 mbar pressure drop over 100 m elevation with specific energy consumption of 0.35 kW/ton - 53% lower than conventional bucket elevators. Material selection studies identify AISI 410 for riser/screw conveyors and AISI 310 for down-comer construction, with erosion analysis projecting a 16-24 year component lifespan. Experimental data demonstrate a controlled particle attrition (<0.1% per cycle) through optimized dense-phase riser and stick-slip down-comer operation. Thermal modeling reveals heat losses below 3% when implementing riser outlet air heat recovery, with additional efficiency gains achievable through solid/air mass flow ratios exceeding 15:1. While confirming large-scale applicability of all unit operations, the study notes potential geometric modifications that may enhance thermodynamic performance in full-scale implementation. The integrated design demonstrates significant advancements in CSP efficiency through particle-based heat capture, storage and recovery optimization and robust material engineering solutions.

Keywords: Concentrated solar tower; particle-driven; conveying; design; attrition; erosion

1 Introduction

The issue of the particle conveying in the CSP technology was addressed during the Next-CSP project in a wide viewpoint reviewing the commercially attractive solutions. Among different options, it was decided to apply a bucket elevator for conveying the cold particles (~300 to 350°C) 12 m high to the cold store silo atop the receiver. Although operating at moderate temperature over a limited vertical height only, the elevator was operationally unreliable due to mechanical wear of chains and sprockets and difficulties to cater for thermal expansion. At higher temperatures (> 500 °C) and higher lifting heights, the mechanical parts (chains and sprockets) should be in an air-cooled enclosure leading to high sensible cooling air heat losses. The power required to mechanically lift the particles is moreover increased by about 220 % because of the weight of chains and buckets and by the mechanical friction. As part of the European-funded "Powder-to-Power" (P2P) initiative, this project investigates the operation of a particle-driven CSP concept on MW-scale. A particle suspension is used throughout the concept as heat transfer medium. P2P will use a fluidized bed-in-tube solar receiver [1–3], a downcomer, a particle PV superheater; a particle storage/power block, and a dense-phase pneumatic lifter to recycle the cold particles to the receiver on top of the solar tower. Such pneumatic conveying system for fine particles (< 80µm) was previously developed and operated in the petrochemical industry for heights exceeding 30 m. Guo et al assessed the use of pneumatic conveying in CSP applications for capacities as high as 600 tph and lifting heights of 250 m [4].

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Attrition and erosion occur simultaneously in fluidized beds, hoppers and their associated pneumatic transport loops. Attrition is mainly defined as a reduction in particle size, erosion determines mostly the wear of the construction materials. Attrition will both reduce the average particles size, this modifying the bed composition; and will increase the dust emissions.

Particle attrition was first studied to characterize catalysts for fluid-cracking fluidized bed reactors, and further explored for all kinds of powder reactors and particle circulation loops [2], [5–7]. Both phenomena of attrition and erosion are not fully assessed yet. It is hence important to evaluate powder systems for various process operations (e.g., bed loss during start-up), to limit fines production and minimize downstream deposits or erosion, to maintain particle reactivity, to reduce operating costs, or toward environmental regulations (e.g., minimize required dust abatement cost) [8–10]. Several sources of attrition are recognized, i.e., particle heating, calcination, sulfidation, low and high velocity impacts. All these sources reduce the particle size through wear, fracture, abrasion, shattering and disintegration. Attrition of solids can also be caused by thermal stress (when particles are being heated or cooled and unequal temperatures in the particles cause uneven expansion); chemical stress (when during a chemical reaction of a particle its surface will generally react first); static mechanical stress (when a particle is stressed at its surface e.g. at the bottom of a bed, or from by e.g. formation of gas or by vaporization of hydration water); and kinetic stress (when moving particles suffer surface abrasion upon collisions e.g., in cyclones, in transport loops, or by high-velocity (grid) jets). Mechanical and kinetic stress are commonly noticed in a fluidized bed especially around the gas distributor where at high orifice velocities play a key role. High attrition rates will enhance particle entrainment. that should therefore also take attrition into considering [11].

Few literature data are available on particle attrition and equipment erosion in transport loops, thus stressing the innovative character of the present research.

Erosion also decreases the particle size, but the wear of the construction material is of greater concern since it may contaminate the bed material, lead to a progressive degradation of the reactor and associated equipment, and will lead to increased maintenance. Erosion is mostly the result of particle impact at high velocity. The sources of attrition and erosion are summarized in Table 1 below.

Table 1. Sources of attrition and/or erosion

Sources of particle attrition	
Mechanical stress	Screw feeder Rotary valves etc.
Kinetic stress	Impact of particles due to: -High velocity jets (orifices) -In conveying lines -Due to bubbling action -Collision with tubes, baffles, ... In cyclones etc.
Thermal stress	Thermal shock of cold particles fed in hot bed.
Chemical stress	Evolving gases, water vapor.
Sources of equipment Erosion	
Mostly as result of mechanical action of particle impact e.g. sparge tubes of distributor, imbedded tubes, instrumentation and probes, bends, cyclones, ...	

Toward the P2P application, thermal and chemical stress do not need to be considered since the applied olivine particles are resistant to thermal shock and are chemically inert.

2 The particle conveying system

2.1 Layout and Principles

Figure 1 illustrates the layout of the proposed particle conveyance system. If to be applied as a large scale, a heat recovery sub-system should be integrated into the loop either by using a heat exchanger (Fig. 1a) or by re-circulating the hot gas after high-temperature filtration (Fig. 1b).

The conveyance of 16 tph particles will be achieved in an insulated lifter pipe of 0.20 m I.D. The pressure drop for 100 m high lifting will be about 250 mbar and the electrical consumption will be ~0.35 kW/ton solids conveyed (against 0.75 kW/ton for a bucket elevator). Heat losses will be minimized as a result of the heat recovery on the conveying air. In this configuration, the mass ratio of particles to air is ~15.

Fig. 2. Overall layout of the P2P particle conveying loop. Thermal expansion is catered for by expansion bellows or flexible connecting ducts.

2.2.2 Upward pneumatic transport

In the riser, the cold olivine particles (~300 °C) are conveyed upward to be stored in the cold storage hopper before being reheated by the receiver.

Due to difficulties of mechanical conveying, pneumatic conveying in medium dense phase was selected. Dense pneumatic transport can maintain large concentrations of solids. A particle dense phase system is mechanically unfeasible due to temperature limitations of the discontinuous blow tanks. The proposed solution will apply a continuous particle-in-air medium dense phase conveying, with lower pressure drop along the conveying pipes. With this method the product is fed into an airflow, produced by a positive air source [13].

Aiming to design the riser, in which the pneumatic transport takes place, some assumptions need to be made. The olivine particles will be conveyed at 16000 kg/h, while having a absolute density of 3300 kg/m³ and a particle size of 40 to 60 µm. The solids-air ratio is considered to be 15 kg solids/kg air through the riser. The riser has a vertical length of max 100 m (incl. a top 90° bend). A high-efficiency cyclone at the end of the conveying pipe will remove the particles from the conveying air.

2.3 Design procedure

The limiting velocities, UCH (vertical) and Usalt (horizontal) were measured and reported. The choking velocity is a crucial parameter in vertical pipelines and represents the minimum velocity the airflow must have to avoid sedimentation to the bottom of the vertical pipe resulting in blockage.

The ultimate property that needs to be known when designing a pneumatic conveying system is the power required to ensure the conveying. For this, the total pressure drop across the pipes has to be known. In moderately dense pneumatic conveying, the pressure drop is affected by four physical factors, which are listed below with their corresponding formulas [14]:

The constituting pressure drops (ΔP) include:

- (i) The ΔP due to gas friction in the conveying pipe;
- (ii) The Δ P from the particle acceleration to the conveying velocity;
- (iii) The Δ P due to the pipe wall friction of the conveyed particles;
- (iv) The Δ P related to the weight of the particles in the riser;
- (v) The Δ P due to the pipe bends.

Important parameters are the step velocity, i.e. the difference between the gas velocity and the particle terminal velocity, the solid/gas ratio, the wall-to-particle friction factor, the effect of an increasing conveying velocity due to depressurization, and of course T-related parameters (gas density and viscosity). Having determined the total pressure drop, the conveying power required to give the air and particles a certain velocity is the product of the total pressure drop and the volumetric air flow rate expressed in Nm³/s. Based on the calculated power, a fan with a certain efficiency can be selected.

$$P = \Delta P_{\text{total}} \cdot F_g \quad (1)$$

The method of calculation and pressure drop equations were previously presented by some co-authors ¹⁴

The gas friction pressure drop, ΔP_{fg} can be calculated by using the Darcy-Weisbach equation (equation 1). In this equation, f_g is the friction factor which is determined by using the Blasius correlation given by equation 2 [14].

$$\Delta P_{fg} = f_g \cdot \frac{\rho_g \cdot v_g^2 \cdot L}{2 \cdot D_T} \quad (2)$$

$$f_g = \frac{0.316}{Re^{0.25}} \quad (3)$$

2.3.1 Riser at 300 °C

Olivine is a typical A-powder, free flowing, with low angle of repose (17 to 19°) and a negligible angle of internal friction. All the fundamental characteristics and operating parameters are listed in Table 2.

Table 2. Fundamental characteristics and operating properties

2.4 Riser at ambient temperature

Particle characteristics	
Olivine mean size	40 to 60 μm
Average absolute particle density	3350 kg/m^3
Average bulk density	1803 kg/m^3
Pipe diameter pneumatic conveying	
Density air	1 kg/Nm^3 (at Thémis)
M^*	≈ 15 kg solids/kg air
M_s	4.444 kg/s
Riser	0.21 m
F_g	900 Nm^3/h 0.25 Nm^3/s 1889 m^3/h at 300 °C, i.e. 0.52 m^3/s
Choking velocity, U_{CH}	6.81 m/s, The velocity in the vertical conveying must exceed U_{CH} .
Saltation velocity, U_{SALT}	16.3 m/s, This is not important in the final loop lay-out, since we avoided horizontal conveying sections.
Acceleration pressure drop	
M_s	4.44 kg/s
F_s	0.00136 m^3/s
G_s	126.9 kg/sm^2
ρ_s	3350 kg/m^3
ρ_{air}	0.48 kg/m^3
μ_{air}	0.00003329 Pa.s
U_g (midpoint)	15.1 m/s
ε	0.995
a_p	0.00459
d_p	0.00005 m
U_t	0.45 m/s
U_s	14.7 m/s
ΔP_{acc}	1865.4 kg/ms^2 0.0187 bar
Pressure drop from the friction of conveyed particles on the tube wall	
$L_{\text{horizontal}}$	0 m
L_{vertical}	90 m
L_{bends}	6 m
L_{total}	96 m
U_g	15.1 m/s
G_s	126.9 kg/sm^2
ΔP_{sf}	14547.6 kg/ms^2 0.146 bar
Pressure drop from the weight of the particles in the riser	
$L_{\text{horizontal}}$	0 m
L_{vertical}	90 m
L_{bends}	6 m
L_{total}	96 m
G_s	126.8 kg/sm^2
ΔP_t	7616 kg/ms^2 0.076 bar
Total pressure drop	
ΔP_{total}	241 mbar 0.241 bar
Velocities	
$v_{\text{top 300 °C}}$	15.0 m/s
$v_{\text{bottom 50 °C}}$	8.45 m/s ($> U_{\text{CH}}$)
Power	
ΔP	24100 kg/ms^2
F_g	0.25 Nm^3/s
Power	6.025 kW, Installed power 10 kW

Since the particle conveying loop must also be able to operate at ambient temperatures, a design compromise with the 300°C design must be made. The important design parameter is the superficial air velocity that needs to exceed the

choking velocity. The riser geometry will remain the same. Due to the higher air density and lower air viscosity, respectively 1 kg/Nm^3 and $2 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}$, against 0.48 kg/Nm^3 and $3.3 \cdot 10^{-5} \text{ Pa s}$ at 300°C , flow parameters will alter.

To operate at a fair velocity, $>10 \text{ m/s}$, the air flow rate must be increased to preferably $1200 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$, providing a superficial air velocity of 11.14 m/s . The solids/air ratio is reduced to 13.45, still in the moderately dense phase conveying mode. The flow Reynolds number is 117000, leading to an air flow friction factor of 0.01711 (against 0.02095 for $900 \text{ Nm}^3/\text{h}$ at 300°C). According to the design method presented for the riser at 300°C , the following pressure drops prevail:

- Acceleration $\Delta P = 13.6 \text{ mbar}$
- Friction $\Delta P = 64 \text{ mbar}$
- Particle weight $\Delta P = 76 \text{ mbar}$

Total pressure drop $\sim 154 \text{ mbar}$

Despite the higher gas flow rate, the low pressure drop decreases the power requirement to 5.1 kW . The installed compressor power of 10 kW is hence certainly applicable.

2.5 Downcomer

The downcomer is filled with powder from the receiver at 16 t/h and has a height of 70 m . Due to the olivine particle density of 3300 kg/m^3 and the particle diameter of $40\text{-}60 \mu\text{m}$, this powder is considered an A-type powder.

Since the downcomer always has an input and output flow subject to gravity, the design of the downcomer is considered the same as that of a silo. The powder has a negligible internal friction angle and angle of wall friction. The outlet diameter of the downcomer is therefore not designed according to Jenike's design method for silos, but the Smolders and Baeyens equation is applied [14].

$$M_p = \frac{3140 \cdot D^{2,7}}{d_{sv}^{0,07}} \quad (4)$$

Alternative practical design equations for the flow in a downcomer, given as the critical solids discharge rate, by Carleton, Rauch and Beverlo were compared in [15,16] yielding downcomer solids flow rates of approximately 12000, 17000 and $>30000 \text{ kg/m}^2\text{s}$.

At the available downcomer surface area of 0.035 m^2 , the possible solids flow rates all exceed 350 kg/s , far in excess of the 4.44 kg s required in the P2P loop, hence offering flexibility for scale-up and/or discontinues operation. If filled, the downcomer has an additional hot storage capacity of 4.5 t .

According to the formula above, the outlet diameter should measure 6.8 cm . Since this equation is based on pilot-scale installations and this project is worked out on an industrial scale, an outlet diameter of 0.2 m is chosen instead of 6.8 cm to avoid clogging problems in the outlet of the downcomer.

2.6 Screw conveyors

This mechanical conveying system consists of commonly used screw conveyors. Such conveyors comprise a rotating screw blade (the main and only moving component of the equipment) located within a sealed U-shaped housing (also called trough or auger). Essential for operation are the trough ends, which support the conveyor drive and end shafts, and also help to maintain shaft and trough alignment. The screw is driven by an external speed-controlled drive and the housing is attached to a couple of supporting hangers, bases and saddles. There are variations in diameter, shape and layout when it comes to the screw blades, each configuration depends on the specific desired function and the material to be conveyed. This conveying method is widely used in bulk handling industries, moving any type of materials regardless of the composition and the size (fine or coarse). Screw conveyors are simple and compact, meaning that they only require an external drive to transport the material and occupy much less space to operate than other material handling systems (which need more space because of the returning part). They can effectively transport solids in a sealed and dust free environment in horizontal, vertical and inclined directions. Screw conveying also has the possibility of having multiple material inlets and outlets throughout the system, material mixing while conveying is also a perk.

The use of the screw conveyors in the P2P concept is foreseen to and from the power block. Their manufacture needs specialized skills. Thomas Conveyor Company offers screw conveyors that can withstand temperatures up to $2000 \text{ }^\circ\text{F}$ ($1093 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Diameters up to 300 mm are very commons as small as 100 mm , whereas diameters up to 300 mm are available. The screws conveyors are usually applied for short hauls (less than 20 m).

For the P2P layout; 2 identical screw conveyors are foreseen; one in horizontal position (from tower to power block) and one in inclined position (from power block to the venturi feeder of the riser. Both conveyors have a diameter of 219 mm. Due to the reflux of particles in the inclined conveyor, its speed of rotation must be higher than in the horizontal operating mode, in this case respectively 60 to 70 rpm against 40 to 50 rpm. The screw conveyors are externally insulated with 100 (inclined, at 300°C) and 150 mm (horizontal, 600°C) with steel cladding. In doing so, heat losses are limited and the cladding wall temperature is well below 50°C.

3 Additional considerations

3.1 Heat losses and mitigation features

Heat losses in the particle conveying loop are of natural convection (from outside wall-to-environment) and of forced (conveying air heated to an equilibrium temperature with the transported solids) nature. To reduce the conductive heat losses, all equipment parts will be insulated with a 100 (low temperature) or 150 mm thick ceramic fibre insulation (600°C). Assuming a 50°C wall temperature and an outside temperature of 20 °C, the heat losses amount to a maximum of 150 W/m². The outside diameter of the screw conveyors and of the riser and downcomer, insulation included, will be ≈ 500 mm. Considering their respective lengths, the total convective heat losses will be

Riser + downcomer: 21205 W

Screw conveyors: 4141 W

Adding 20% for all points of transfer (e.g. venturi feeder of riser), the total natural convective heat loss will be 30.5 kW.

Considering the heat load of the 4.44 kg/s particles, at a C_p of 1.2 kJ/kgK with a ΔT of 300 °C, the particles in circulation represent a total heat flow of 1595 kW. Natural convective heat losses will hence represent a maximum of 1.9%.

The heat losses due to the pneumatic conveying are limited to the riser only. The particle movement in the downcomer and in the screw-conveyors are air-free. The particles will be fed to the riser at 300 °C, and the air flow rate will be 0.25 Nm³/s at 50 °C (after compression). A heat balance fixes the equilibrium out temperature at 285,6 °C. The heat losses amount to 76,6 kW. As a ratio of the heat load of the particles, this represents a heat loss of about 4,5%. It should however be remembered that mitigation measures can be included in the final assessment and scale-up of the operation. The conveying air, after dedusting, can be sent to a heat exchanger to preheat the conveying air to 150 – 200 °C. this will involve the addition of an air duct from the receiver level to the venturi feeder of the riser, but will reduce the air-related heat losses by 63.4 kW, thus leading to a convective heat loss of 13.2 kW only, i.e., 0.9%. The recycling of the hot outlet conveying air to the venturi feeder is of higher technical difficulty, since fans and blowers operating at 300 °C, possibly with a limited number of ultrafine particles present, and capable of compressing the hot air to 1,3 bar (or higher pressures for a larger scale than the P2P pilot) are very expensive and not commercially available.

3.2 Thermal expansion of the equipment

Whatever stainless steel is selected, the thermal expansion is significant, and close to 16 to 18 μm per m length and per °C. For a 17m long screw conveyor, it will be limited to 8 cm (300 °C) and 16.7 cm (600 °C). The conveyors will hence have 1 fixed point and be allowed to expand along the length. Connections with the receiving fixed points will be established by flexible metal tubes. For the 70m downcomer, at a maximum T of 600 °C, the expansion will be 69 cm. Since the operation is pressure- and airless, a simple mechanical seal is envisaged at the bottom of the downcomer.

For the 90m riser, the expansion will be limited to 27 cm, due to the selected stainless steel. The thermal expansion at the top of the riser will be catered for by a bended connection to the evacuation tube, and a flexible metal compensator (e.g., AE 22 of AXCES) between the bend and the evacuation piping.

4 Particle Attrition and Erosion

4.1 Experimental Investigations

Numerous experiments were carried out for long-duration (1000 h) in the rig of Fig.3. This rig is representative for particle conveying loops. Both straight conveying lines, bends and gas-solid separation are included, and experiments at high temperature are possible.

Fig. 3. Test ring for attrition and erosion measurements

To assess the powder behaviour during mechanical screw conveying, a separate experimental rig was used (Fig.4). An impeller tumbler was inserted in a Habersham electric furnace; and used for olivine at temperatures up to 700 °C. Experimental results of both rigs will be illustrated below. Only essential results toward P2P design and operation are reported.

Fig. 4. Schematic of the abrasion setup. The left image shows the movement of specimens through olivine particles

4.2 Attrition in the conveying loops

4.2.1 During pneumatic conveying

Two solid/air ratios were tested, i.e., 4.4 kg solid/kg air and 20.4 kg solid/air. The former loading is representative for dilute conveying [17,18], whereas the latter represents dense-phase conveying and dense-phase cyclones [3], [19], [20]. Results are presented in Fig.5.

Fig. 5. Particle size versus operating time at varying solids/air conveying ratios (at $U=15$ m/s) and 700°C)

Temperature was shown to have a negligible effect, when the air velocity remained constant. The velocity of 15 m/s is representative of the P2P conveying objectives.

No particle agglomeration was noticed (no increase of d_{90}). A small amount of particle breakage (attrition) was measured but less than 0.08% of the weight. For 16 000 kg/h in the loop, about 12.8 kg/h of fines will be created to be captured and re-used (cyclone and filtration) and recycled in the system, but finally it also means that we will need to replace some of the bed material every 2 or 2 months.

4.2.2 Attrition in screw conveyors

Results using the impeller tumbler are a lot better. Specimens are mounted onto a rotating shaft and continuously rotated through a bed of olivine placed inside a trough. This setup also allows to simulate operation at the low-speed dense granular flow conditions expected in the storage hoppers during discharge, in the screw conveyors, and through the fluidized bed heat exchangers. The system design also ensured a stagnant zone of particle contact with the auger material. The wear from particle impact on the wall is nearly negligible and abrasion wear is not observed.

The unique design allows the setup to be operated inside a Habermann kiln maintained at temperatures up to 900°C . The temperature distribution inside the kiln was verified using thermocouples to ensure that the particles and the test specimens reached a maximum temperature of 700°C before commencing the experiments. Two setups were built for independent testing at room temperature and inside a kiln. The shaft can be loaded with up to 6 different specimens simultaneously and the relative velocity between the particles and the containment specimens is controlled by using a speed-controlled motor. Rotational speeds of up to 25 rpm were tested. The depth of the particle bed is kept such that the specimens are completely submerged.

Experiments demonstrated that the operating temperature has no effect on the particle attrition. After 1000 h, particle sizes were reduced from $78\ \mu\text{m}$ to $74.4\ \mu\text{m}$. These size reductions are negligible in views of the operation time. The obvious reason is the creation of a stagnant particle layer near the auger bottom. The level of attrition in the P2P mechanical conveyors can hence be considered as negligible.

4.3 Particle-driven erosion of the construction materials

4.3.1 Erosion rates

In many applications a surface is attacked by solid particles entrained in a fluid stream. This type of wear is generally described as erosion. Erosion is a continuing problem in such units as pneumatic conveying equipment. While usually considered undesirable, erosion has useful applications in such processes as sand blasting, abrasive deburring and the erosive drilling of hard materials.

Previous research by P2P team members established that erosion is only detrimental to construction materials if the particle velocities exceed about 30 m/s. In the P2P application, velocities will be below 15 m/s and erosion is therefore considered less of a problem.

In the mechanical transport equipment (screw conveying) no erosion was measured, due to the protective particle layer formed near the conveyor's auger (mixing blades end at about 1 mm from the auger's wall).

The situation is different in the pneumatic loop. Since the construction material contains ~25 wt% of Cr, the evolution of erosion can be determined from the measured Cr concentration in the particle flow. Samples of the olivine were collected, Cr was leached by nitric acid, and the resulting solution was submitted to ICP-MS measurement. The most relevant results are illustrated in Fig.6 below.

Fig.6. Erosion rate for 2 solid/air (S/A) rates in the pneumatic conveying rig, at a velocity of 15 m/s and 600 ° C

The Cr concentration is expressed in µg/kg olivine in circulation. The erosion rate is limited to 0.6 µg/kg after 1000 h. with 106 m³/h (138 kg/h) of air and a solid rate of respectively 606 (S/A= 4.4) or 2811 kg/h (S/A = 20.4), the amount of metal wear is maximum 1.68 mg/h. Considering a total weight of the experimental steel construction at about 90 kg, or 22.5 kg Cr, the hourly erosion rate is 0.0075%.

This is a very acceptable erosion rate, even in the operational case of 16 000 kg/h of solids circulating through the pipe and associated auxiliaries, It is however recommended to specifically address the construction of the bends, preferably in an inverted L shape, to accumulate a static layer of solids, and having “low” bends (radius of curvature equal to 6 x pipe diameter) to avoid high velocity impact on the – otherwise – 90 ° angled bends.

4.3.2 Selection of construction materials for the P2P plant

4.3.2.1. Preliminary considerations

The potential construction materials must be capable of operating at high temperature and withstand the thermal cycling between different process conditions. The possible corrosion in an oxidizing (air) atmosphere is an additional key issue. A preliminary selection based upon a few relevant criteria is presented in Fig.7.

Thermal and mechanical properties will additionally need to be considered and will determine the required geometry (pressures to deformation and rupture; wall thickness). Standards such as ASTM A240, ASTM A555, and testing standards ASTM E139 are important. The steel and alloy properties are commonly given in handbooks or in technical leaflets of suppliers. These properties are not commonly available for ceramic materials; although mostly alumina is recommended for its ease of production; treatment, and its moderate cost. Alumina composites; zirconia, or silicon carbide and nitride can also be used. Other alloys such as Hastelloy, FeC-alloy and Iron Aluminide, were also tested but only for comparative reasons. Their applications in the solar P2P plant is exhibitiv towards cost and unnecessary better behaviour when exposed to the temperatures under scrutiny. It is however clear that AISI 310 has a fair to excellent behaviour in high temperature and oxidizing environments. It is moreover 2 to 3 times cheaper than Incoloy and more readily available on the market of steel suppliers.

Fig. 7. Selection of piping and vessel construction materials

4.3.2.2 Experimental assessment

The P2P research investigated these mechanical properties.

(1) Mechanical properties after thermal cycling

Using six identical samples of AISI 310 tubes (39 mm O.D.; 2 mm wall thickness), with one cylindrical element not being subjected to the T-cycling (used as blank), the effect of thermal cycling was assessed. Five pipes were subjected up to 1000 cycles of heating to 800 °C in an electric furnace, and air cooling at 200 °C. Pressure resistance testing was performed in a pull/press laboratory unit of Feiyao Hydraulic. Pressures to deformation varied from 14.8 MPa for the virgin tube, to 14.1 MPa after 1000 cycles. Under the same conditions, the pressure to burst achieved 41.6 to 39.4 MPa, respectively. Both experimental critical pressures correspond with calculated values by the Barlow equation. The calculated wall thickness required at as high a pressure as 5 bar and 800 °C was < 0.03 mm, far below current commercial pipe thicknesses. In the P2P operations, high pressures are not encountered (maximum 1.3 bar in the receiver and upflow riser). Other equipment will be subjected to a maximum pressure load of 100 mbar. Wall thicknesses of 2 mm are hence certainly sufficient to guarantee a long cycle-life.

(2) Corrosion testing

Corrosion testing assesses the performance of the materials suitable for the manufacture of the various elements; investigate the effects of fabrication methods on service performance, and determine the maximum operation temperature. These materials again covered various alloys, including a number of welded specimens. The materials in the screening test included various compositions of AISI 316L, AISI 310, Inconel 601, Inconel 625 and Incoloy 800 HT. The conditions for the screening test provided a relatively severe but realistic simulated process gas for a hot component of a solar reactor system. Specimens were exposed for 1000 hours. Air was used, as the gas applied in P2P. Its flow rate was set by flow rate control and mixed before feeding the furnace. The ambient humidity conditions of the air were accepted. Before cooling the furnace at the end of the test, N₂ was applied to flush the test gas.

For **Weight change testing**, the furnace specimen holder was cooled in air and were placed into a desiccator before weighing. Each specimen was visually inspected and weighed to assess the rate of corrosion product lost during the tests. For numerous specimens (e.g. AISI 316L), significant amounts of the corrosion product layer had spalled. The weight gain due to the formed oxide layer is limited for most of the materials rested and measured between 3 and 20 mg/cm² for e.g. Inconel 690 and AISI 310. After weighing the complete specimen, the oxidation protection layers were pompously detached with a weight loss of 5 to 32 mg/cm² as the result.

For **Corrosion measurement**, the specimens were sectioned, they were encased in a thin layer of resin (Epofix) to protect the corrosion product layers during cutting. The sections were then cold mounted in resin before grinding and polishing to a 1 μm finish. Each section was viewed using an optical microscope to measure the thickness of the oxide layers and identify other features related to the exposure. Results are summarized in Fig. 8.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the oxide thickness layer between blank and temperature cycled spacemen (shaded). When no bars are shown, measurements are below measurement accuracy)

Optical microscope imaging revealed that the damage rate during 1000 h experiments can be expressed in $\mu\text{m/hr}$ of damaged alloy surface. The maximum damage rate ($\sim 0.1 \mu\text{m/hr}$) in air was revealed for Hastelloy X. Haynes D205 and Iron aluminide showed the lowest, maximum damage rate of $< 0.001 \mu\text{m/hr}$. The damage rate of other alloys was between 0.001 and $0.05 \mu\text{m/hr}$.

These values are low in oxidizing conditions, and mostly below $0.015 \mu\text{m/hr}$. The life duration of a 2 mm thick pipe will exceed 66000 hours (~ 16 years at 4000 h/year).

5 Conclusions

Using the fundamental and practical findings of the research presents the final design and operation recommendations for the P2P pilot plant and toward a future scale-up were presented. Dimensions and properties of the riser (upward conveying to the top of the solar tower) and of the down-comer (gravitational transport of receiver particles to the bottom of the tower) are first examined with a full specification of internal diameter, operating air flow rates, pressure drops and installed blower power.

The construction materials of the P2P loop were evaluated. A good evaluation of metal strength (at operating temperatures) and cost lead to the selection of AISI 410 for both riser and screw conveyors. The down-comer will be manufactured using AISI 310 steel alloy.

From assessing the erosion rate of the metal constructions as presented in a previous Solar PACES paper, it was determined that the erosion damage will be limited and will guarantee an equipment lifespan of 16 to 24 years.

Attrition of particles will be limited in the screw conveyors, in the dense-phase riser; and stick-slip flow down-comer.

Heat losses were calculated, and can be reduced to less than 3% if the riser outlet conveying air is used to preheat the riser feed air. Also operating at higher solid/air mass flow ratios will significantly reduce the air-driven losses. It is finally concluded that all unit operations of the present particle conveying loop can be applied on a large-scale, although some geometric modifications might be required.

The results of different investigations with respect to the particle attrition and particle-driven erosion behaviour in function of the temperature lead to a selection of possible construction materials. These results determine the design and operation of the P2P concept. The impact is summarized in the following Table 3.

Table 3. Fundamental properties

Property	Values and comments	Impact
Particle attrition in the pneumatic conveying loop	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a small amount of particle attrition was measured; higher at high solid/air ratio than at low ratio - temperature has no significant effect - the attrition rate is less than 0.08 wt% of the particle conveying rate at high solid/air conveying ratios 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - velocity in the lifter (vertical conveying loop) should be preferably limited to 15 m/s - limited effect of temperature - for the P2P application, with a solids circulation rate of maximum 16 ton/h, the creation of fines will be about 12.8 kg/h (see particle size, below). These fines need to be collected in the (gas) solid separation unit.
Particle attrition in mechanical conveyors (μm)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - at rotational speeds of 10 to 25 rpm the particle attrition lowered the particle size by less than 6% after 1000 h. - temperature effects are negligible. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no effect of operating temperature - provide a stagnant particle layer between the scroll (impellers) and the auger walls.
Particle agglomeration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no increase in d_{90} was measured - no agglomeration occurred 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not of specific concern
Particle-driven erosion in pneumatic conveying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - erosion rate of construction material is $< 0.0075\%r$ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - special attention is needed for high velocity particle impacts in the bends by either using bends of high radius of curvature, and/or construct the bends in inverted L-shape
Particle-driven erosion in mechanical conveying	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - no erosion of construction materials was measured, due to the static particle layer underneath the scroll (impeller) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - not of specific concern.
Dust emission	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - limited to the quantity of fines in the feed olivine, and to the number of fines formed in the conveying loop 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - fines of the feed olivine will be collected at start-up - operational fines (max. 1278 kg/h, will need continuously collected
Emission abatement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - from the various solid-gas separation techniques, the cyclone offers advantages of simplicity and maturity - measurements using a High-efficiency Stairmand cyclone reveal a capture efficiency at high temperature in excess of 96% for 1.5 μm, dust - the high particle density of olivine counteracts the expected efficiency loss due to the higher operating temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the use of a Stairmand or Van Tongeren High-efficiency cyclone operating at 3.6 m/s is recommended. - the cyclone pressure drop will be less than 15.3 mbar (against 20 mbar at 4 m/s)
Construction materials	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - AISI 310 offers excellent properties and has a high resistance to deformation and bursting. - it is moreover a lot cheaper and more widely available on the steel markets/ - the oxide layer formed, protects the underlying steel matrix from oxidative corrosion - the damage rate is between 0.001 and 0.05 $\mu\text{m}/\text{ht}$ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - construction of all equipment should be performed in AISI 310. Only for parts at 900°C (e.g. receiver tubes) could Incoloy 600 be a better solution. - the damage rate is low and a 2 mm thick pipe will have a life duration of about 16 years. A 3 mm thick pipe will be operational for at least 24 years.

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Declarations

The authors declare no competing financial interest. Data available on request from the authors.

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